

8T – Strong Interaction Paradox

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T and in particular the confinement of Quarks inside the "sea" of Gluons, as net curvature which increases the probability of arrival of other net curvature to its position, author will reason for the fact that in high energy the Strong interaction getting weaker. That is because high energy is synonymous with trying to roll the Quarks up hill, or to change the lowest energy state, which means in terms of Gluons to make the curve more flat.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equation (1) By (1.2A) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation (1). We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the idea of Quark confinement using that framework, stating that each net curvature is increasing the probability of arrival to its position. The end result is endless cluster of Gluons inside the hadron, which causes the Quark triplet to position on the lowest point on the curve. At high energy trying to break the triplet is synonymous with trying to roll the distinct arbitrary amount of curvature up hill, or to flatten the curve. The illustration below is the Quark triplet before collision, as presented in the 8T thesis, page sixty-nine.

At high energy, there exist a hadron collision that leads to immense increase of the energy, which is synonymous with trying to roll the Quarks up-hill:

As the number of Gluons in the cluster is infinite, the illustration is not accurate, as the Quarks seems to be separated and to reach the height of half of the curve. In reality the moments the triplet are separated in hadron collission, they will aspire again to the lowest point on the curve, in other words, they will accelerate toward one another. That is the elements that differ sign toward one another. The second illustration can be represented in a different manner, somewhat resembles relativity in different frames of reference. The Quark triplet is the same, it's the curve itself that is getting flattened. The fact that the curve is flattened means that the quarks are less bounded that before, and at a stage where the curve is completely flat the Quarks are no longer confined. Such a construction can reason for the fact that the strong interaction is getting weaker at high energy, as the curve itself is effected by an additional amount of matter, assuming the curve is negative given by the Ricci flow:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = -2Ric$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i < 0 \quad (1.49.A)$$

That term (1.49.A) is effected by positive energy given by (1.48) which is the colliding hadron, so overall the negative amount of net curvature decreases, causes the curve to get flatten, after the collission, the net curvature which retained, will causes the extra net curvature to reach its positon and the original curve will be retain, with the original Quark triplet locked to the minima. So at high energy the term representing the strong interaction is a weaker term, i.e. the 8 + (1) and not just the one. At high energies than:

9: 30: 128

The idea of the curve flattening due the positive energy on the hadron and the negative sign of the curve is given by the below illustration:

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad